

Carbonyl Stretching Frequencies and Electronic Spectra of Rhodium(I) Monocarbonyl Complexes.^a

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Substituted monocarbonyl trans-Rh(CO)XL₂ complexes, where L is triphenylarsine (AsPh₃) and triphenylstibine (SbPh₃); X=F, Cl, Br, I, CN, SCN, SeCN, NO₂, NO, and ClO, and their adducts with sulphur-dioxide and tetracyanoethylene (TCNE) have been prepared and characterised. The infrared and electronic spectra of these compounds have been reported. The carbonyl stretching frequencies (ν_{CO}) in Rh(CO)XL₂ and in their SO₂ adducts follow the increasing sequence X=F<Cl<Br<ClO₄<I<NO₂(?)<SCN~NO₂<SeCN<CN and the influence of anionic ligands X on (ν_{CO}) values has been explained. The nature of TCNE adducts has also been discussed.

RHODIUM(I) having d⁸ configuration is known to form a large number of square planar monocarbonyl trans-Rh(CO)XL₂ complexes, where L=PPh₃ and X is an unidentate anionic ligand¹⁻³. But the corresponding AsPh₃ and SbPh₃ analogues have not been fully characterised. Hence we have prepared trans-Rh(CO)XL₂ complexes, where L=AsPh₃, X=F, Cl, Br, I, ClO₄, NO₂, NO₃, CN, SCN, SeCN; L=SbPh₃, X=F, Cl, Br, I, NO₃, CN and isolated their adducts with SO₂ and TCNE in order to explain the shifts in carbonyl stretching frequencies in all these complexes. The electronic spectral data of these compounds have been discussed.

Experimental

The substituted monocarbonyl complexes were prepared by the following general methods: The lemon yellow solution⁴ obtained by refluxing 0.5 gm of RhX₃.xH₂O (X=Cl, Br) in 50 ml dimethylformamide (DMF) was treated with 0.3 gm of L when Rh(CO)XL₂ (L=AsPh₃, SbPh₃) were obtained as pale yellow and bright red crystals respectively. The SbPh₃ compound was recrystallised from chloroform and ethanol. The NO₃ compound was obtained from 0.8 gm of Rh₂(CO)₄Cl₂ by treating first with 0.4 gm of AgNO₃, sublimation in vacuum followed by bridge splitting by AsPh₃ or SbPh₃⁵. The other compounds Rh(CO)XL₂, where X=F, I, NO₂, ClO₄, CN, SCN, SeCN; L=AsPh₃ and X=F, I, CN, SCN; L=SbPh₃ were all prepared by the simple method of metathesis from the chloro-analogues:

M=K, X=NO₂, SCN, ClO₄, M=Na, X=I, CN,

SeCN, M=Ag, X=F and solvent is dry acetone or methanol (in case of ClO₄). A typical preparation is given below: 0.7 gm of Rh(CO)Cl(AsPh₃)₂ was treated with 0.5 gm of NaI in 60 ml dry acetone for 30 min. It was cooled, filtered and evaporated under vacuum when pale yellow solid appeared, it was recrystallised from benzene by adding hexane. All the compounds were oven dried before analysis.

The SO₂ adducts were prepared from respective monocarbonyl complexes by passing dry SO₂ gas through the solutions of the latter in either benzene or chloroform kept in ice and acetone mixture in a Dewar's flask¹. After some time the solution slowly turned green and the green crystals were obtained by rapid vacuum evaporation. Since SO₂ adducts are unstable under normal conditions, (they can be preserved over SO₂ atmosphere) only the analysis of rhodium could be carried out. The TCNE adducts were isolated by adding a freshly prepared solution of TCNE in benzene to the solution of the parent compound in the same solvent⁶. The solvent on slow evaporation yielded the yellow to brown solids. The analytical data for the monocarbonyl complexes and their adducts with SO₂ and TCNE are given in the Table 1.

The i.r. spectra (4000-400 cm⁻¹) of the compounds in nujol mull and chloroform (cell thickness 0.02 mm) were recorded on Carl-Zeiss Specord 75 IR instrument provided with a grating device. In every case the transmittance and base line were adjusted as far as practical. The carbonyl stretching frequency region was scanned repeatedly with different speed and control. The accuracy of i.r. band remains within $\pm 1-2$ cm⁻¹. The electronic spectra of the monocarbonyl complexes were run (40000-20000 cm⁻¹) using a Specord UV-VIS spectrophotometer. In case of all the compounds

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA* FOR THE COMPOUNDS Rh(CO)XL₃, Rh(CO)XL₃SO₂ AND Rh(CO)XL₃TCNE

Compounds	X	Rh (%)	Rh (%) in SO ₂ adducts	N (%)
Rh(CO)X(AsPh ₃) ₃	F	13.5 (13.49)	12.6 (12.45)	
	Br	12.6 (12.49)	11.2 (11.60)	9.6 (9.71) ^b
	I	12.1 (11.82)	12.3 (12.21) ^a	14.2 (14.55) ^b
	NO ₂	12.9 (12.78)	11.9 (11.84)	1.7 (1.74)
	NO ₂	13.2 (13.04)	12.1 (12.06)	1.8 (1.77)
	SCN	12.7 (12.84)	11.7 (11.89)	1.7 (1.75)
	CN	13.2 (13.37)	12.3 (12.35)	1.8 (1.82)
	SeCN	12.1 (12.13)	11.1 (10.99) ^c	1.6 (1.65)
Rh(CO)X(SbPh ₃) ₃	ClO ₄	12.2 (12.21)		4.8 (4.20) ^b
	F	12.1 (12.00)		
	Br	11.5 (11.22)		8.8 (8.71) ^b
	I	10.7 (10.67)		13.5 (13.16) ^b
	NO ₂	11.5 (11.45)		1.5 (1.56)
	SCN	11.6 (11.50)		1.5 (1.56)
TCNE adducts of Rh(CO)X(AsPh ₃) ₃	CN	11.8 (11.92)		1.6 (1.63)
	F	11.6 (11.56)		6.3 (6.29)
	Cl	11.3 (11.35)		6.1 (6.18)
	Br	10.3 (10.28) ^d		
	I	10.8 (10.82)		5.9 (5.89)
	NO ₂	10.2 (10.31)		5.6 (5.61)
	SCN	11.1 (11.02)		7.6 (7.5)
				7.5 (7.5)

* The calculated values are given in parentheses. (a) Analysis for chloro adduct. (b) Analysis of halogens. (c) The metal analysis in Rh(CO)Cl(SbPh₃)₃SO₂. (d) The metal analysis in Rh(CO)Cl(SbPh₃)₃TCNE.

TABLE 2—CARBONYL STRETCHING FREQUENCIES (IN CM⁻¹) FOR MONOCARBONYL COMPLEXES

X	ν _{CO} (in cm ⁻¹) ^a						Bending Rh-C-O modes in Rh(CO)X(AsPh ₃) ₃
	Rh(CO)X(AsPh ₃) ₃		Rh(CO)X(SbPh ₃) ₃		[Rh(CO)X(PPh ₃) ₃] ₂ ^a	Rh(CO)X(PPh ₃)(AsPh ₃) ₂ ^a	
	Nujol	Solution	Nujol	Solution	Nujol	Nujol	
F	1955	1970	1950	1966			590 s, 560 w.
Cl	1964	1978	1960	1975	1980	1960, 1959**	570 s, 540 w.
			1960†				
Br	1966	1980	1965	1978	1982	1964	565 s, 530 w.
I	1980	1982	1980		1985		545 s, 520 w.
ClO ₄	1976						550 s,
NO ₂	1970	1988	1966				565 s, 545 w.
SCN	1988	1990	1962		2001	1983	532 s, 515 w.
NO ₂	1983	1992					598 s, 520 s, 510 s
SeCN	1986	1996					
CN	1990	2003	1996				

^a All the bands are very strong.
^{*} Ref. 9
[†] Value for Rh(CO)Cl(SbPh₃)₃.
^{**} Value for Rh(CO)Cl(PPh₃)(SbPh₃)₂.
^{***} Value for Rh(CO)Cl(PPh₃)₂(SbPh₃)₂.

the solution was made in benzene (10⁻³ – 10⁻⁵ M); (in chloroform and dioxane for the TCNE adducts), the cell thickness was 0.996 cm.

Results and Discussion

While lemon yellow solution of RhCl₃.xH₂O in DMF reacts with PPh₃ and AsPh₃ to produce trans-Rh(CO)XL₃ complexes, it consumes a large excess of SbPh₃ to form the compound Rh(CO)Cl(SbPh₃)₃ (found Rh-8.73%, Cl-3.2%; calculated for Rh(CO)Cl(SbPh₃)₃ Rh-8.39%, Cl-2.89%). However, the

latter on repeated recrystallisation from chloroform and ethanol is converted into trans-Rh(CO)Cl(SbPh₃)₃ and the colourless crystals of SbPh₃ are collected in the upper edge of the container when the filtrate after recrystallisation process is evaporated. Similarly the isolations of {Rh(CO)Cl(SbPh₃)₃}₂.C₆H₆ and mixed ligand compound Rh(CO)Cl(SbPh₃)₂(PPh₃) have been reported from Rh₂(CO)₄Cl₂ and [Rh(CO)Cl(PPh₃)₃]₂ respectively⁷⁻⁹. Moreover, by carrying out the reaction in CH₂Cl₂ with four fold excess of SbPh₃ trans-Rh(CO)Cl(SbPh₃)₃ is produced which is same as our recrystallised product. It is significant

to note that the carbonyl stretching frequencies in all these different SbPh_3 compounds remain virtually the same, (see Table 2). The present work and earlier studies⁷⁻⁹ indicate that SbPh_3 has the tendency to form five co-ordinate carbonyl complexes with rhodium(I). It is found that five co-ordination tendency of the group V donor atoms increases along the order: $\text{N} < \text{P} < \text{As} < \text{Sb}$.¹⁰ Probably the longer metal (low spin d^8)-antimony bond distances allow less steric hindrance so that more SbPh_3 ligands can be accommodated around the central metal atom.

Further we found that in the isolation of $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})\text{FL}_2$ using a suspension of yellow crystals of AgF in dry acetone¹ gave better results subject to the following essential precautions: (i) temperature of the reaction mixture should be kept at ca. 50° ; (ii) as far as practicable absolutely dry solvents are to be used so as to minimise the moisture content in the reaction mixture; (iii) the reaction should be carried out in subdued light, the reaction vessel should not be exposed to direct light for long; (iv) freshly prepared yellow silver fluoride (which darkens on prolonged exposure to light and atmosphere) must be used. All the pseudohalogeno ligands NCE ($\text{E} = \text{O}, \text{S}, \text{Se}$) are expected to be N-bonded in $\text{trans-Rh}(\text{CO})\text{NCEL}_2$ where $\text{L} = \text{AsPh}_3$ and SbPh_3 .¹¹⁻¹⁵ The strong tendency of $\text{Rh}(\text{I})$ and $\text{Ir}(\text{I})$ to form bonds with N and not with E of NCE groups may be due to the presence of strong π -withdrawing groups—one CO and two L's (phosphine, arsine, stibine, etc.) in $\text{trans-Rh}(\text{CO})\text{NCEL}_2$. This bonding approach* termed as 'co-operative electronic effects' has been discussed by Tulco and Pecile¹⁶. Like PPh_3 analogues⁸ the fluoro, perchlorato and nitrate compounds ($\text{L} = \text{AsPh}_3$) show some conductances specially in presence of donor solvents such as MeOH, DMSO (dimethylsulphoxide) suggesting solvent induced dissociation:

The carbonyl stretching frequency data for monocarbonyl complexes $\text{trans-Rh}(\text{CO})\text{XL}_2$ are given in Table 2; the values for some dimeric compounds $[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})\text{XL}]_2$ and mixed ligand complexes of the type $\text{trans-Rh}(\text{CO})\text{X}(\text{PPh}_3)\text{L}$ have also been

* X-ray and i.r. data suggest¹⁷⁻²¹ that in $\text{Fd}(\text{II})$ complexes containing different kinds of phosphine ligands, the thiocyanato ion may co-ordinate through both $-\text{N}$ and $-\text{S}$. It has been argued that π -bonding hypothesis to explain N-bonded SON in $\text{Fd}(\text{II})$ compounds is incompatible with the findings of Cartv et al.¹⁷. This is specially true because there exist different opinions regarding the hardness and softness of ML_3^+ fragment^{22,23}. The objections to π -bonding hypothesis was also raised by Singh and Varshavskii²⁴. It would appear that the steric effect can also influence the choice of bonding sites in NCE ion^{22,25}. But, this suggestion seems to have been largely ignored in favour of π -bonding hypothesis which is more in vogue and forthright at present.

quoted in the same table. As expected, the ν_{CO} values occur in the region $1990\text{-}1950\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in all these complexes. In order to compare the ν_{CO} values we have selected isostructural and formally isoelectronic complexes. This in part will ensure that CO stretching frequencies will be influenced by only X ligands (and also by L's situated at cis-position to CO). From Table 2 it appears that the sequence of ν_{CO} in $\text{trans-Rh}(\text{CO})\text{XL}_2$ ($\text{L} = \text{AsPh}_3, \text{SbPh}_3$) and total electronegativity values of anionic ligands are almost same as those for $\text{trans-Rh}(\text{CO})\text{-X}(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ compounds^{1,3}. The carbonyl stretching frequency values in these compounds and in dimeric $\text{trans-}[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})\text{XL}]_2$ and in $\text{trans-Rh}(\text{CO})\text{XL}'\text{L}''$ increase in the order $\text{X} = \text{F} < \text{Cl} < \text{Br} < \text{ClO}_4 < \text{I} < \text{NO}_3 < \text{SCN} \sim \text{NO}_2 < \text{SeCN} < \text{CN}$ although the magnitude of increase becomes less prominent towards higher range ca. $>1980\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for $\text{L} = \text{AsPh}_3$ and SbPh_3 . Since the sequence of X is retained in different types of $\text{Rh}(\text{I})$ compounds this phenomenon may be considered to be of general nature. The position of NO_3 ligand is little confusing because while in nujol null the location of this anionic ligand in all the $\text{trans-Rh}(\text{CO})(\text{NO}_3)\text{L}_2$ compounds comes closer to bromo ligand and it lies in between Br and I, in solution spectra ν_{CO} value for NO_3 compound moves closer to that for SCN. Similar situation prevails in $\text{trans-Rh}(\text{CO})\text{NO}_3(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ [compare data $\nu_{\text{CO}}(\text{nujol}) = 1970\text{ cm}^{-1}(\text{NO}_3), 1969\text{ cm}^{-1}(\text{Br})$ and $\nu_{\text{CO}}(\text{CS}_2 \text{ solution}) = 1982\text{ cm}^{-1}(\text{NO}_3)$ ²⁴]. The immediate reason for this behaviour of nitrate ligand is not understood but it is probable that the tendency for nitrate compound to dissociate in solution might be responsible for this. The best explanation which can account for above order can be offered on the basis of π -bonding ability of X which includes two components of π -interactions—formally these may be regarded as π -acceptor and σ -donor abilities of the ligands. In this respect the σ -donor ability is of less significance^{24,26}. The ligands having suitable empty d_π (Cl, Br, I) or other π -orbitals, e.g., π^* orbitals (CN can have empty π^*_v and π^*_h orbitals) which are capable to withdraw metal d_π electrons can be said to possess π -acidity or π -acceptor ability. On the other hand, the ligands X such as CN, SCN, NO_2 , NO_3 which contain filled π -bonding orbitals and are capable of donating electrons to empty p_π orbitals of the metal can be considered as having π -donor ability: filled $\pi(\text{X}) \rightarrow$ empty $p_\pi(\text{M})$. Since the π -bonding ability or more precisely π -acceptor strength of halo ligands varies as $\text{I} > \text{Br} > \text{Cl} > \text{F}$ the ν_{CO} values increase in the sequence $\text{F} < \text{Cl} < \text{Br} < \text{I}$. For ligand CN we have highest ν_{CO} value in the series because CN like CO can act as both good π -acceptor and π -donor. That is why in CN the carbonyl group has the strongest contender for d_π electrons of $\text{Rh}(\text{I})$ and also the strongest donor to empty metal p_π orbital. Almost similar explanation can be offered for the position of NCS and NCSe ligands in the series for which the ν_{CO} values are lying closer to (but definitely less than) that of cyano compounds indicating that they are having less π -bonding ability

than CN and probably it decreases along the series $CN > CNSe > CNS$ within the limit of these pseudohalogeno ligands. We find that the π -acidity order of Vaska⁸ viz. $CN > NCSe$ (not given by Vaska) $> NCS$ is in agreement with that of ours. For NO_2 ligand the bonding π -orbital extending over three atoms (N,O,O) and containing four delocalised electrons is expected to involve in π -interaction with Rh(I), similar behaviour is also envisaged for NO_3 anion²⁷. Some authors^{24,27,28} suggest that the π^* orbital above and below the NO_2 and NO_3 planes are of low energy and therefore these anions may also in principle withdraw the electron density from filled d_{π} 's of Rh(I). Thus both these interactions would cause a shift in ν_{CO} values to higher region. From above it thus appears that depending on their π -interaction ability we can divide the anionic ligands into three groups to which three distinct sets of ν_{CO} values can be assigned. These are (i) OH^* , F (ca. $\nu_{CO} \leq 1970 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)-hard bases having no π -donor-acceptor ability; (ii) halo ligands including sometimes NO_3 ion (ca. $\nu_{CO} \leq 1980 \text{ cm}^{-1}$); which are soft bases can also exhibit π -acidity and (iii) the pseudohalogeno ligands including NO_3 ion (ca. $\nu_{CO} > 1980 \text{ cm}^{-1}$)-which are soft bases can function as both π -acids as well as π -bases.

The SO_2 adducts of $trans-Rh(CO)XL_2$ ($L = AsPh_3$ and $SbPh_3$) containing S bonded SO_2 ^{29,30} are

essentially tetragonal pyramidal^{1,31} (TGP), where p_z orbital of rhodium becomes engaged due to donation from SO_2 .

Under the circumstances, the ν_{CO} values in $Rh(CO)XL_2(SO_2)$ should depend only on the π -acceptor strength of X ligands. The carbonyl stretching frequencies collected in Table 3 show that the trend of ν_{CO} decrease in these adducts follows the order: $F < NO_3 < NO_2 < Cl < Br < SCN \sim CN$ which is the same as reported for $trans-Rh(CO)X_2(PPh_3)_2$ earlier¹, excepting the positions of NO_3 and NO_2 . Thus it appears that the contribution of the π -interaction involving metal d_{π} orbital at least in this type of adducts is more important in assessing the influence of X ligands on ν_{CO} values. The important i.r. bands in TCNE adducts are collected in the Table 3. From i.r. data the following is observed: (i) there is a sharp increase in ν_{CO} values in TCNE adducts and in few cases $\Delta\nu_{CO}$ [$\nu_{CO}(\text{TCNE adduct}) - \nu_{CO}(\text{parent compound})$] values correspond to a shift of $\sim 100 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in chloroform solution. In nujol mulls many of the compounds show two or three carbonyl bands. The nujol spectra of recrystallised Cl, Br, I and SCN compounds containing $AsPh_3$ (and also PPh_3) reveal that the relative intensities of ν_{CO} peaks depend upon the recrystallisation. In the process of recrystallisation usually the lower ν_{CO}

TABLE 3—THE CARBONYL STRETCHING FREQUENCIES (in cm^{-1}) FOR THE ADDUCTS OF $Rh(CO)XL_2$ WITH SO_2 AND TCNE

X	ν_{CO} (in cm^{-1})				Other bands		
	Adducts with SO_2		Rh(CO)X($AsPh_3$) ₂ , TCNE		Nujol	Solution	
	$AsPh_3$	$SbPh_3$	Nujol	Solution			
F	2020s		2110ms, 2070s		2065s	2230ms	
Cl	2035s	2038s	2090w, 2070s, 2050m, 2025w		2070s	2253sh	2255s
Br	2040s		2070s, 2055w*		2072s	2227ms	2235br
			2098s, 2078s, 2055w (α) 2070s, 2050w*		2104s	2230ms	2235br
I			2100ms, 2070m, 2055w* (β) 2080s, 2072m ^a			2235ms	2237s
			2080s, 2070w* 2100s ^b			2235ms	
NO_2	2025s		2070s, 2055m 2074s, 2055mw*			2230ms	
SCN	2044s		2100s** 2065m, 2055s			2252m,	2250m,
					2085s	2233ms,	2240ms,
			2089s*			2080s ^c	2090s ^d
CN	2045s						2095s ^d
NO_3	2030s						
Cl^e			2075s			2235m	

- (a) First crop.
- (b) Crop from filtrate after long standing or after evaporation.
- (c) ν_{CN} for SCN in nujol (see reference 24).
- (d) ν_{CN} for SCN in chloroform.
- (e) Value for $Rh(CO)Cl(SbPh_3)_2$, TCNE.
- (*) Compound after recrystallisation.
- (**) After evaporating the solution on water bath.

* The data for $AsPh_3$ and $SbPh_3$ compounds are not available, ν_{CO} $Rh(CO)OH(PPh_3)_2$ - 1961 cm^{-1} (ref. 9).

band gradually diminishes while the intensity of higher carbonyl band records an increase. If the spectra of same compounds are run in chloroform solution only one band is observed. Almost similar situation is reported for $\text{Ir}(\text{CO})\text{X}(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ -TCNE compounds³². The probable cause of splitting of ν_{CO} bands in these complexes is the presence of two or more geometrical isomeric varieties (rather than solid state effect), where TCNE remains bonded either through olefinic linkage producing five co-ordinated species [here two probable structures viz. TGP or TBP (trigonal bipyramidal) are possible] or through σ -bond forming 'rhodium cyclopropane ring'^{6,34} yielding six co-ordinate compound. In chloroform solution, the appearance of only one ν_{CO} band is probably due to rapid isomerisation of unstable variety/varieties to the more stable one. We presume that (nujol spectra) ν_{CO} (max) corresponds to the quasioctahedral compounds and ν_{CO} (min) to trigonal bipyramidal species. The comparison of the i.r. spectra ($600-500\text{ cm}^{-1}$) of $(\text{CO})_2\text{Rh}(\mu\text{-Cl})_2$ - $\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2$ of free AsPh_3 , $[\text{Rh}(\text{CO})_2\text{Cl}_2]^-$ and of $\text{trans-Rh}(\text{CO})\text{X}(\text{AsPh}_3)_2$ reveals two bands for the last type of compounds. The high intensity bands in the higher region and low intensity ones in the lower region have been tentatively assigned to 'out-of-plane' vertical bending $\delta(\text{Rh}-\text{C}-\text{O})_v$ and to horizontal $\delta(\text{Rh}-\text{C}-\text{O})_h$ modes respectively. These assignments are in agreement with the data for other carbonyl complexes³³⁻³⁷. It is interesting to note (see Table 2) that $\delta(\text{Rh}-\text{C}-\text{O})_v$ deformation

Fig. 1. Relationship between ν_{CO} and $\delta(\text{Rh}-\text{C}-\text{O})_v$

decreases in the order $\text{F} > \text{Cl} > \text{Br} \sim \text{NO}_2 > \text{I} > \text{NO}_2$ (?) $> \text{SCN}$ which is almost reverse to the sequence of X noted for ν_{CO} shifts. The relationship between vertical bending mode and carbonyl stretches is shown in the Figure 1. The enhanced rigidity of

vertical deformation $\delta(\text{Rh}-\text{C}-\text{O})_v$ is obviously caused by the interaction $\pi_v(\text{CO}) \rightarrow$ vacant $p_z(\text{Rh})$ and the above order of X is the consequence, at least partially if not wholly, of the above rigidity effect which is influenced by the anionic ligands.

The electronic absorption spectral data for monocarbonyl complexes and their TCNE adducts are given in Table 4, other related spectral

Compound	E_{max} in μm^{-1}	$\epsilon M^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$	λ_{max} nm
$\text{Rh}(\text{CO})\text{X}(\text{AsPh}_3)_2$			
Cl	3.34, 2.81	1204, 4417	299, 355
Br	3.23, 2.79	2208, 2008	309, 358
I	3.22, 2.76	1225, 6666	310, 362
SCN	3.33, 2.76	9839, 3413	300, 362
CN	3.35, 2.68	7630, 7530	298, 373
NO ₂	3.23, 2.73	4016, 4819	309, 366
$\text{Rh}(\text{CO})\text{X}(\text{SbPh}_3)_2$			
Cl	3.24, 2.72	8617, 3406	308, 367
$\text{Rh}(\text{CO})\text{CIL}_2\text{TCNE}$			
PPh ₃	3.25, 2.70, 2.30	2685, 2064	307, 370, 434
AsPh ₃	3.34, 2.83	1204, 1255	299, 353

quantities are also quoted in the same table. We have observed two electronic absorption bands—one appearing at ca. 33000 cm^{-1} and the other at ca. 28000 cm^{-1} for the compounds of the type $\text{trans-Rh}(\text{CO})\text{XL}_2$ with selected anionic ligands. The general feature of the bands are the same as reported by Geoffroy and Mason for $\text{trans-Rh}(\text{CO})\text{-Cl}(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ ^{38,39}. There is no doubt that the electronic absorption bands in planar Rh(I) species are due to metal to ligand charge transfer (MLCT) transitions³⁹. Out of these two the longest wavelength spectral band belong to MLCT $4dZ^2 \rightarrow b_1$ transition ${}^1A_1 \rightarrow B_1$ (1B_1); the high energy bands have been assigned to ${}^1A_1-B_2(2)$ ³⁸. We have observed that lowest bands in $\text{trans-Rh}(\text{CO})\text{X}(\text{AsPh}_3)_2$ follow the order for X:

$$\text{Cl} > \text{Br} > \text{I} \sim \text{SCN} > \text{NO}_2 > \text{CN}$$

$$\mu\text{m}^{-1} = 2.81 \quad 2.79 \quad 2.76 \quad 2.76 \quad 2.73 \quad 2.68$$

which is almost similar to the series reported for $\text{trans-Rh}(\text{CO})\text{X}(\text{PPh}_3)_2$ (with the exception of NO_2 ion). The electronic data series for X is almost the reverse of what have been found from ν_{CO} values. The order of X as observed in electronic spectra can be explained on the basis of rationalisation suggested by Vaska et al³⁹. The electronic spectra of TCNE adducts with $\text{trans-Rh}(\text{CO})\text{CIL}_2$, where $L = \text{PPh}_3$ and AsPh_3 need special consideration. These spectra have the following peculiarities: (i) two absorption bands, at ca. 32500 cm^{-1} and ca. 28000 cm^{-1} are observed in chloroform, benzene and dioxane solutions; (ii) in benzene solution, however, another band appears as a distinct hump at ca. 23000 cm^{-1} ; (iii) while the high energy bands in all the solvents are remarkably similar for the

TCNE adduct, the low energy band shows splitting with the absorption maxima appearing at ca. 27800 cm^{-1} and at ca. 26700 cm^{-1} . These bands in chloroform and dioxane are not symmetric. In benzene solution, however, this band appears at ca. 28000 cm^{-1} as a broad symmetric band with very little tendency to show splitting. In benzene solution, the appearance of bands are very similar to those for trans-Rh-(CO)Cl₂. From these observations it may be suggested that these absorptions are probably due to Rh(III) compounds. In benzene solution, the TCNE adduct suffers reversible dissociation which contains predominantly trans-Rh(CO)Cl₂ as the main species. In chloroform and dioxane solutions such dissociation is not observed. Moreover, the unsymmetrical appearance (twin structure) of the band at ca. 28000 cm^{-1} may be due to the distortion of octahedral structures. This is obvious from the fact that TCNE adducts actually form quasi-octahedral compounds containing metal cyclopropane ring⁶. That the TCNE adducts undergo reversible decomposition in benzene solution becomes apparent from the fact that no ν_{CO} band at ca. 2070 cm^{-1} appears for Rh(CO)Cl₂TCNE in benzene solution. The same solution after evaporation produces a compound which reveals ν_{CO} band in nujol mull or in chloroform solution at ca. 2070 cm^{-1} as well as ν_{CN} band at ca. 2225 cm^{-1} .

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